

Verification of Non-Destructive Evaluation for C/C composites using Electrical Technique

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SUMMARY

An establishment of evaluating fiber-matrix interfacial condition at the stage of fabrication is required to apply C/C composite for structural components. In this study, non-destructive evaluation using electrical method was focused. The impedance measurement for the C/C specimens with several conditions of interface was performed.

Keywords: C/C composites, NDE method, Electrical, Mechanical properties interface property

1. INTRODUCTION

C/C composites are expected to be applied to some aerospace structures which are exposed to high temperature, because of the C/Cs' high strength and high toughness at above 2273K. In addition to these mechanical properties, the density of C/C composites is lower than that of other refractory metals. However, several issues are still left to apply C/C composites for aerospace structures.

In the present study, non-destructive evaluation is focused. It is well known that C/C composites include many inner defects which may be caused during manufacturing process. Among these defects, interfacial delamination plays a significant role for the reliability of C/C composites. It was reported that fiber-matrix interfacial condition greatly influences the mechanical properties of C/C composites [1].

X-ray, ultrasonic scanning and SQUID have been considered for non-destructive evaluation of C/C composites. However, only large defects such as a transverse cracks and voids can be detected by these techniques and small defects like inter laminar debonding (<1mm) are not possible to be detected [2].

Therefore, in the present study, apart from the above methods, an electrical nondestructive evaluation method was tried by measuring the impedance of the heat-treated C/C composites. In addition, the correlation between electrical data and mechanical properties was confirmed.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1. Materials

Unidirectional C/C composite reinforced with high-modulus carbon fibers, Torayca M40 was used in this study. This C/C composite was produced by a preformed yarn method (Across Co.Ltd.Japan) [3]. The fiber volume fraction of the C/C composite was 50%.

2.2. Controlling interfacial debonding by oxidation

Oxidation resistance depends on location, that is, fiber, matrix, and fiber-matrix interface, in C/C composites; the highest oxidation takes place along the fiber-matrix interface [4,5]. At low temperatures, the material is oxidized at a uniform rate irrespective of location, surface or center, of the materials (chemical-reaction-rate-controlling regime)[4,6]. Thus, in the present paper, interfacial situation between fiber and matrix was controlled by oxidation treatment (1~5hrs) at low temperature (823K). The specimens were heated to the desired temperature (823K) for oxidation in nitrogen. When the desired temperature was reached, the atmosphere gas was switched from nitrogen to air. All the specimens were placed in a stainless box as shown in Fig. 1 and oxidized in a flowing air.

Fig.1 Schematic view of stainless box used for oxidation treatment

The polished cross-sections of both the original and the oxidized C/C composites were observed by a SEM in order to calculate the rate of debonding between fiber and matrix. The rate of debonding was calculated by eq. (2-1) where the “debonding($^{\circ}$)” indicates the debonding region between the fiber and matrix in terms of the circumferential angle. When all fiber-matrix interfacial debonding occurred around a fiber, the rate of debonding is 100%.

$$\text{rate of debonding}(\%) = \frac{\text{debonding}(\text{^{\circ}})}{360(\text{^{\circ}})} \times 100 \quad (2-1)$$

2.3. Mechanical testing

2.3.1. Push out testing

The interfacial strength of the C/C composites was evaluated using a single fiber push out method illustrated in Fig. 2, where the thickness l of samples was $50\sim 100\ \mu\text{m}$. In this method, the interfacial fracture was induced by a load applied with a spherical indenter to single fiber which was placed parallel to the loading direction as shown in Fig. 2 [7]. When the load saturated during the push out test, this constant load was esteemed to be the shear failure load, P and the interfacial strength τ was calculated by eq. (2-2).

$$\tau = \frac{P}{2\pi \times r \times l} \quad (2-2)$$

where r is the radius of carbon fiber.

Fig.2 Schematic of push out test.

2.3.2. Shear testing

The shear strength of the C/C composites was evaluated using Double-notch-shear test (DNS) with a fixed crosshead speed of $0.1\text{mm}/\text{min}$. The test was complied with ASTM-D3848. The configurations of the specimens used for DNS are shown in Fig. 3, where the distance l between two notches of samples was fixed to 6mm [8]. The shear strength τ is calculated by eq. (2-3)

$$\tau = \frac{P}{l \times w} \quad (2-3)$$

where P is the fracture load, and w is the width of the sample.

Fig.3 Specimen configuration for DNS.

2.3.3. Tensile testing

The specimen size was $150 \times 5.0 \times 3.0$ mm and tensile tests were carried out using a screw driven testing machine at a constant crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min.

2.4. Explorative experiment of debonding

In order to examine the influence of debonding on electrical property, some electrical tests were performed using samples with debondings in the bonding layer.

Two glassy carbon plates ($13 \times 55 \times 3.0$ mm) were bonded by phenolic resin. After bonding, the sample was carbonized at 1773K in argon atmosphere. Electrical properties were evaluated using four-point electrode method by which the contact resistance occurred during the test can be cancelled. In the electrical test, the impedance Z , the resistance R and the reactance X were measured with 10kHz in 5A at impressed current $A_{p.p}$. The impedance Z can be calculated with eqs. (2-4) and (2-5).

$$\frac{1}{Z} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{R^2} + X^2} \quad (2-4)$$

$$X = \omega C - \frac{1}{\omega L} \quad (2-5)$$

2.5. Tensile testing after electrical test

2.5.1. Electrical testing

Electrical properties were evaluated using the same method as article 2.4 and as shown in Fig. 4. In this study, the resistance R , the capacitance C and the inductance L were supposed to be placed parallel as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig.4 Specimen configuration and schematic of electrical test.

Fig.5 Diagrams of Parallel circuit.

2.5.2. Tensile testing

In order to verify correlativity between the reactance X and the tensile strength of C/C composites, tensile tests were performed to the samples the electrical properties of which was measured. The testing machine and the cross-head speed were the same as article 2.3.3.

2.6. Positional identification test of debonding.

In order to confirm the capability of detecting debonding region, electrical tests were performed to locally oxidation-treated samples. To realize local oxidization, the samples were oxidized in a stainless steel case which has a hole at the center as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig.6 Schematic of local oxidation procedure.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Controlling interfacial debonding by Oxidation

Figure 7 shows the cross section of untreated and oxidation-treated C/C composites. As can be seen in these photographs, the fiber-matrix interfacial debonding occurred in the oxidized C/C composite. Figure 8 shows the rate of interfacial debonding, which was calculated by eq.(2-1). The debonding rate increased in increase of oxidation time.

Unoxidation

Oxidation for 5 hours

Fig.7 SEM observation of C/C cross-section.

Fig.8 Relation between rate of debonding and oxidation time.

3.2. Mechanical properties

The effects of interfacial debonding to the mechanical properties are shown in Fig. 9. From the result of the push out test, it was made clear that the interfacial strength of the C/C composites degraded with the increase of the debonding rate, whereas the tensile strength was enhanced. These results coincides with the well-known fact that the tensile strength of C/C composites increases by decreasing the bonding strength of the fiber-matrix interface, because the interfacial debonding protects the reinforcing fiber from damage due to matrix cracking [9-13].

Fig.9 Effect of rate of debonding on mechanical properties.

3.3. Explorative experiment of debonding

Figure 10 shows a SEM photograph of bonded specimen. As can be seen, the bonding layer has debonding which size is similar to interfacial debonding between fiber and matrix. In this study, the debonding in the bonding layer is named as simulated-debonding. The reactance X of sample including simulated-debonding is slightly higher than that of the original carbon. From eq.(2-5), the capacitance C and the inductance L contribute to increase of the reactance X . In this case, the inductance L has no effect on the reactance change. So, it was suggested that the increase of reactance was caused by the existence of interfacial debonding which acts as a capacitance C .

Fig.10 SEM photograph of bonding layer.

3.4. Electrical testing of C/C composite

Figure 11 shows the relations of the impedance Z and the reactance X versus the oxidation time. In this figure, the normalized impedance Z/Z_0 and the normalized reactance X/X_0 are defined by the ratio of measured value and the average values Z_0 , X_0 of original C/C composites. The impedance Z/Z_0 increased with the increase of oxidation time as shown in Fig. 11. From other data by the same electrical test, the electrical resistance R increases in the increase of debonding rate. Therefore, the main reason for the increase of the impedance Z is esteemed to be the increase of the electrical resistance R caused by the decrease of the current-carrying part due to the interfacial debonding. The reactance X/X_0 increased with the increase of oxidation time as shown in Fig. 11. As suggest in 3.3 the interfacial debonding behaved as capacitance C . So the reactance X increased with the increase of the interfacial debonding.

Fig.11 Relation between oxidation time and electrical properties.

3.5. Tensile testing after Electrical test

Figure 12 shows the relation between the reactance X/X_0 and the tensile strength. With the increase of X/X_0 up to 1.1, the tensile strength of C/C composite is enhanced. The enhancement of tensile strength and the increase of reactance were caused by the increase of interfacial debonding. In the region of X/X_0 being more than 1.1, the tensile strength degraded with the increase of the reactance X/X_0 . Not only the fiber-matrix interface but also the carbon fibers themselves in the C/C composite were oxidized by excess oxidation. The oxidation-damage fiber caused the degradation of the tensile strength of C/C composites. The increase of reactance X was caused by the effect of interfacial debonding and the oxidation-damage fiber by oxidation. In the case of C/C composite, the increase of interfacial debonding causes enhancement of tensile strength. On the other hand, the tensile strength is degraded by the oxidation-damage fiber. So the understanding of the effect of interfacial debonding and oxidation damage is needed to improve reliability of the electrical method.

Fig.12 Relation between tensile strength and the value of reactance X/X_0 .

3.6. *Positional identification testing of interfacial debonding.*

Figure13 shows the reactance of locally oxidized sample. As can be seen in Fig.13, the reactance increased at the center of the sample where the local oxidation was applied. Thus, the electrical test is useful to identify the interfacial debonding.

Fig.13 Effect of debonding on reactance.

4. Conclusions

During a series of tests, the following conclusions were obtained:

- (1) The impedance Z and the reactance X increased in the increase of the oxidation time.
- (2) The tensile strength could be estimated from the data of electrical test.
- (3) The interfacial debonding could be identified by the electrical test.

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